

THE ANALYSIS OF TAX ON IMPORT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. On this article, the author explained import tax, discussed statistic data of import during the period of time: from 2011 to 2023. All information was taken from the official website of World Bank. As well as, she tried to give some explanations about the table and the diagram.

Keywords: GDP, import tax, tax revenue, tax on international trade.

Today's globalization period taxes on international trade plays an important role when interpreting to the world market. Therefore, countries try to implement taxes on international trade on this way: neither the local government suffers from decreasing its tax revenue, nor the foreign entrepreneurs will pay a lot of taxes in order to attract foreign investors.

Taxes on international trade mean entrepreneurs whose main activities are import and export, must pay taxes when they importing goods, services from other countries and exporting goods, services to other countries. Taxes on international trade can be divided into 2 groups: tax on import and on export. On the following table import tax collected in the Republic of Uzbekistan between 2011 and 2023 years is given:

years	tax on import (% of tax revenue)	tax revenue (% of GDP)	GDP (current \$)	import tax (current \$)
2011	4.92926	12.3662	\$60,178,909,2	\$366,830,0
	6874	5676	97.2	48.64

20	5.09073	13.1744	\$67,517,349,2	\$452,821,0
12	0983	0777	12.1	75.92
20	5.35100	13.8004	\$73,180,037,9	\$540,408,7
13	6962	7989	14.9	03.40
20	5.90656	13.4703	\$80,845,385,8	\$643,236,3
14	6067	9298	09.5	36.66
20	5.50166	13.5577	\$86,196,264,7	\$642,939,2
15	0224	5403	55.3	84.25
20	4.60186	13.4329	\$86,138,288,6	\$532,477,9
16	1813	6306	44.2	55.77
20	5.18686	10.3687	\$69,703,222,2	\$374,872,5
17	0136	4701	82.7	76.38
20	3.65266	12.6952	\$58,695,899,0	\$272,182,4
18	3422	9008	92.1	02.89
20	4.02222	11.3019	\$67,293,639,7	\$305,910,7
19	8115	6511	98.4	07.84
20	4.42575	13.4020	\$66,443,265,4	\$394,101,9
20	2017	2762	18.3	21.93
20	4.84593	13.3629	\$77,340,060,0	\$500,821,3
21	4294	0256	03.0	41.92
20	5.61880	11.9887	\$90,095,926,5	\$606,907,7
22	5187	4028	67.4	48.86
20	8.01226	11.5296	\$102,641,879,	\$948,195,1
23	4846	953	248.8	32.40

Table 1: Tax on import of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2011-2023 years¹

As I have said earlier, on the table tax on import (percentage of tax revenue), tax revenue (% of GDP), the amount of GDP and import tax (current US \$) from

¹ It was done by the author according to the data of World Bank

2011 to 2023. It can be seen from the table from the beginning of the period to 2016 there was a slight rise. However after 2016 the trend fell. It is because in 2017 the difference between soum depreciation to dollar according to the Central Bank of Uzbekistan and on the market were equalized. So there was a fall, however in soums the GDP increased than that in 2016. From 2017 to the end of the period the trends rose, ending about 948 million US dollars.

On the following diagram information about import tax was given between 2011 and 2023.

1-diagram. Import tax collected in Uzbekistan, 2011-2023 years²

According to the diagram, the smallest number in the period was in 2018. During the period there was a fluctuation and from 2018 to the end of 2023 the trend rose and in 2023 import tax reached its biggest point. It is because that nowadays the government gives more privileges and opportunities both importer companies and exporter companies in order to develop its economy and bonds with other countries.

References:

1. www.worldbank.org – the official website of World Bank

² It was done by the author according to the data of World Bank